

Measuring Value Creation of BI in the Logistics Industry

Roozen, D.

d.r.h.roozen
@tilburguniversity.edu

Oteng, O.

o.h.j.oteng
@tilburguniversity.edu

Adouti, A.

a.adouti
@tilburguniversity.edu

Brinkhuis, S.

s.brinkhuis
@tilburguniversity.edu

ABSTRACT

Data collection and analysis have been the core of Business Intelligence (BI) for many years. The process of using data will only grow with the rise of Industry 4.0, because partial factors such as big data, make it possible to gain more data at a faster rate. This makes it possible to gain a competitive edge over other companies. Currently, there is a need for a new framework which measures value creation of BI decision making within the logistics industry, since existing frameworks are not capable of doing so. Literature review has been conducted and shows that research falls short in measuring the value creation of BI. This study makes use of literature review with two objectives in mind: getting a better understanding of value creation through BI in the logistics industry and metrics/frameworks which are used for measuring value creation. Business research is essential since implementing BI is a costly task and it should be clear on how companies can benefit from BI.

KEYWORDS

Business Intelligence, logistics, value, framework, metrics, data, information.

INTRODUCTION

The fourth industrial revolution is on its way, as acknowledged by the World Economic Forum (2016). An upcoming aspect of the Industry 4.0 revolution is Business Intelligence (BI).

Data collection and analysis have been the core of BI for many years. The logistics industry has also changed over the years (Barreto, Amaral, & Pereira, 2017). Due to the innovations of BI technologies, it is not only about transporting goods, reducing time and costs along the supply chain anymore. The focus is now more on what to produce, where to produce and where to store. Also in what quantities to produce and who to choose as logistic provider.

These questions are now all part of the decision making mechanism within the logistics industry.

BI is believed to be a great tool to improve the decision-making process for both operational and strategic matters. However, no hard evidence has ever proven this popular believe (Bordeleau, 2018). This research will critically analyze a widely recognized framework which is meant for measuring the value creation of BI. It has been proven for several industries that this framework is valid for measuring the added value of BI. This research will investigate whether this framework can also be applied to the logistics industry.

PROBLEM INDICATION

Despite BI being regarded as one of the most helpful tools in business decision making, the added value in operational and strategic decision making that BI creates cannot be fully measured. Bordeleau (2018) reviewed 42 articles regarding the added value of BI in the logistics industry. He found that all of these 42 articles were not able to demonstrate how BI adds value to operational and strategic objectives.

On the other hand, according to Ahmed, Yusof, and Oroumchian (2019), a framework to measure the added value of BI does exist. Their study verifies the so-called three-stage business value framework for BI, which was proposed by Trieu (2017). This framework was developed to potentially provide a theoretical framework for understanding how organizations obtain value from BI systems. It shows a comprehensive end-to-end view of the processes through which business value is obtained from BI systems.

However, the industries included in the study of Ahmed, Yusof, and Oroumchian do not contain the logistics industry. This can be considered a knowledge gap in the existing literature. This research aims to investigate whether Trieu's framework can also be applied to the logistics industry to close this knowledge gap. In order to

achieve this, a qualitative research approach is chosen which will contain literature review combined with an interview.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Given the established knowledge gap, the following research question was formulated:

‘To what extent can Trieu’s BI measurement framework be applied to the logistics industry?’

In order to answer this research question, we need to investigate more about BI and the logistics industry. The following sub-questions were compiled:

- *‘What does BI mean to the logistics industry?’*
- *‘What are the advantages of using BI in the logistics industry?’*
- *‘What are the disadvantages of using BI in the logistics industry?’*
- *‘How does BI contribute to the performance of the logistics industry?’*

RESEARCH METHOD

To answer the research question of this study, it is vital to determine a suitable research method. This research has a qualitative approach. The nature of this research is inductive, since it aims to create new knowledge. BI assists in management decisions, and since decision making is a human process, interviews are the most suitable way of collecting data. Interviews help to describe, interpret and contextualize a specific concept or phenomena (McCombes, S. 2019). One interview will be conducted with a professor specialized in operations management within the logistics industry. This interview is semi-structured, to measure both the actual quantitative influence of BI on the financial results, as well as the social decision-making process.

This interview is part of case study research, as explained by Yin (2009), a case study is an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not evident.

As this methodology is less controlled and more interpretive, the validity and reliability need to be closely monitored. Monitoring will be done by carefully drafting the interview questions using a

model created by Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson, and Kangasniemi (2016). This model is specifically designed for semi-structured interviews.

In addition, literature regarding the added value of BI has been obtained. The academic paper “Understanding the Business Value Creation Process for Business Intelligence Tools in the UAE” Ahmed, A., Yusof, S. A. M., & Oroumchian, F. (2019), has been a substantial element of this study. This paper builds on the framework of Trieu (2017), which provides a comprehensive end-to-end view of the processes through which business value is obtained from BI systems. With the data collected and the knowledge obtained from the literature, it can be determined whether this framework can also be applied to the logistics industry.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

In this research, ‘the use of BI tools’ is the independent variable. ‘The added value in the logistics industry’ is considered the dependent variable. The relationship between the independent and dependent variable is affected by other variables:

- Whether a company is B2B or B2C
- Whether a company is large or small
- The reason behind implementing BI

These variables are considered moderating variables as they affect the relationship (Sekaran, Bougie, 2016). The implementation motivation is believed to be a quasi-moderator as it has a direct influence on the added value in logistics industry.

DATA COLLECTION

The data for the study was collected through a single telephonic semi-structured interview. Due to the travel distance, the interview was held over the phone instead of a face-to-face interview. The interviewee was chosen based on certain criteria:

- The interviewee has to have a significant role within the logistics industry,
- He/she needs to have experience with Business Intelligence and Big Data

- He/she needs to work within the Industry or close to the Industry.

The key reason for choosing these criteria for recruiting a suitable participant was that a person with considerable knowledge (e.g. has completed a relevant study with regards to the logistics industry and/or BI) of the logistics industry was needed for this study. Hence why the person interviewed for this study was the most suitable, as he provided an in-depth understanding of use and value-creation of BI within the logistics industry. The interviewee has a PhD in the field of logistics.

The participant was found through a mutual acquaintance. After the respondent agreed to participate, he was contacted via email to schedule a video call interview. After obtaining approval from the interviewee to record the interview, the interview was recorded and transcribed for data analysis purposes. The duration of the interview was approximately 30 minutes and the questions of this interview were based on the sub-questions that have been formulated in this research. The interview protocol was designed using the research questions and the model created by Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson, and Kangasniemi (2016), as is described in the research method.

RELIABILITY

Multiple factors are taken into account to increase the reliability of the data collection process. There is no (in)direct connection between the researchers and the interviewee which otherwise could have potentially led to biased responses. The interview also took place in a quiet environment through Skype calling to prevent any potential interruptions. The interviewers made sure to only ask open-ended questions which allowed the respondent to answer the questions more freely. The interview is also recorded, transcribed, documented and analysed to achieve precise results. All of these factors add to the reliability of the results.

VALIDITY

All of the interview questions are taken into consideration with all four members of the research team. Taking the interview questions into consideration this way is done to ensure the research questions are as valid as possible and provide the information needed to answer the research question. The interview questions are formulated after all the members of the research team did their research on existing literature about the topic. Having all members do their research on existing literature results in interview questions that are more relevant, which also adds to the validity of the data collection process.

RESULTS

The meaning of BI for the logistics industry

Business Intelligence is important for the logistics industry. It is an aspect that has long been underexposed by logistics companies, particularly in the warehouses. Many companies struggle to maintain an overview of their significant amounts of data, which also makes using the data difficult for them.

Since the rise of increasingly modern software, many software packages are available for companies which allows them to gain insight based on big data. This enables them to take smarter actions. For example, setting up a more efficient warehouse, determining which products to keep and which products to push off. In that sense there is a lot of potential, especially for the smaller companies.

Business Intelligence contribution to cost savings in logistic companies

It turns out that implementing BI mostly originates from attempting to fix an issue within the company rather than trying to be innovative. To solve the problem, business cases are created and various analyses are done which result in a BI related solution.

Data made available by BI can lead to useful insights about for example inventory costs, administration costs, run times et cetera. In this sense, BI will also contribute to having more certainty. The ground rule is: having access to more information and being able to share this information will almost always lead to cost reductions.

Types of BI tools in the logistics industry

Systems such as Power BI and Tableau are widely used within the logistics industry.

Advantages of these software tools are:

- Monitor and create data visualizations
- Power BI is an integrated building block
- Relatively cheap and user friendly

In Intralogistics, warehouse management systems play a large role in the Netherlands. A commonly used system, for example, is Manhattan. It is all about connecting and integrating the logistics systems. Lastly, the size of the company also determines the choice between a custom package and a standard solution.

Advantages of using BI

Smaller companies differ from larger companies when it comes to the maturity of the logistics department. Within the sector it is seen that larger logistic companies are often more professional and have more structured business processes. For the smaller companies, the logistics department often functions as a support department with high costs. Because logistics is not their core business, smaller companies do not invest a lot of money in it, and thus also not in BI.

Also, the nature of a company determines the added value of BI. For Business to Consumers (B2C) companies such as 'Bol.com' and 'Coolblue', logistics is an essential part of their business model. They can bind customers by delivering goods as quickly as possible. Due to the lack of attention it receives from smaller organizations, it is an opportunity that can be taken to earn or save a lot of money. It is still relatively "new" and the direct competitors usually do not use it either. This gives the opportunity to become an innovative leader in the logistic segment.

Disadvantages of using BI

Sometimes, obtaining information becomes the sole purpose and that causes other factors to be overlooked. For example, with the use of BI, it is possible to trace back how long it took an employee to finish a particular task. This could lead to micro management and privacy violations. To prevent this, the ethical side of BI always needs to be taken into account. Just because you can measure something, does not mean that this is ethically accepted.

BI contribution to the performance of logistics companies

Nowadays, customers want to know where their purchased products originate from. The chains are getting longer, which means that it is no longer simply the case that a company produces a product and sends it to the customer. These days more and more often companies on the other side of the world create product, after which it passes through all kinds of intermediate stations to adjust or add elements before it finally reaches the customer. By keeping track of all these steps, it is easier to trace back where something went wrong. Tracing and analyzing the error makes it possible to dive deeper into the processes and make them even more efficient by removing bottlenecks.

Moreover, it is more often seen that within the logistic sector new terms such as BI are phenomena

that many companies are interested in, but do not really know what to do with them. It is more a desire to participate in the latest development.

MEASUREMENT METHOD

Currently, there is no specific way of measuring the added value of BI in the logistics industry. The effectiveness of BI is mostly seen in the way it solves a current issue at hand as described earlier. This can be in the form of cost reduction or higher earnings.

Even though the value of BI is currently not actively measured within the logistics industry, there are measurement methods and frameworks available for a more detailed approach to measure added value than just cost reduction or higher earnings. The question is whether or not these frameworks also apply to the logistics industry.

DISCUSSION

BI is important for the logistics industry, an aspect that has long been underexposed by logistics companies. From the results it is seen that BI is currently used mainly within the logistics industry to solve current issues or to cut costs. While our interview has shown that BI can, amongst other things, help deliver goods as quickly as possible and because of the late adoption within the sector, competitive benefits can be achieved.

The results show why and how logistic companies can benefit from BI. BI has not yet been widely accepted within the sector, especially by the smaller companies.

As has been mentioned before, this research has its limitations. The most significant limitation is the validity, specifically focusing on how the data for this research has been collected. The data collection of this research has been solely accumulated from one interview, which makes the sample size of this study too small and unrepresentative to the entire logistics industry.

For this reason, the results that have been acquired cannot be generalized to the entire logistics industry, which in turn increases the likelihood of a Type II error skewing the results, which decreases the relevance of the study (Anderegg, Callaway, Boykoff, Yohe, & Root, 2014). In addition, our study is largely based on the added value of BI in logistic firms. For a deeper understanding of the added value of BI this needs to be focused by

specifically looking at the added value of BI on logistic processes. Therefore, further work is needed to explore in detail the added value of BI on logistic processes.

Another limitation of this research was time. Due to the deadline, it was not possible to perform a full and elaborate literature research within the given time frame. This is also the explanation for the unrepresentative sample that has been acquired for this research. The last limitation the researchers faced was that they were not able to study on every piece of valuable literature.

CONCLUSION

There are multiple conclusions to be drawn from the results:

BI is and will remain of significant importance for the logistics industry and can result in competitive advantages. Moreover, the importance of BI might continue to grow, especially for smaller companies.

Cost reductions and maximizing profit are the main reasons for using BI within the logistics industry. Rather than being innovative, BI is used as a problem solver.

The size and nature of a company determine what and how much added value can be achieved through the use of BI. For instance, 'smaller' companies do not give BI the attention it deserves, because of its high costs. However, investing in BI might result in opportunities in which small companies can become innovative leaders.

BI might also entail disadvantages. A prime example is that companies can get obsessed with measuring as much as they can which leads to them overlooking other important factors.

In most cases, companies do not actually understand BI and its uses. It is seen as a trend that they want to participate in the latest developments, rather than acquiring substantive knowledge.

The framework developed by Trieu (2017) can be seen in Figure 1 and consists of the following components:

- The BI conversion process
- The BI use process
- The BI competitive process
- Context and environment factors

Based on these overlapping processes, Trieu (2017) shows that proper investments in BI assets can lead to a so-called "BI impact" which in turn can lead to better organizational performance. This framework was presented and tested on various sectors which

showed that this framework is a valid method for measuring the added value of BI. The logistics industry was not included in this research, but based on the knowledge gathered from our interview and literature review, we were able to analyze and conclude that the implementation of BI within logistics does not differ from other sectors when it comes to measuring the added value of BI.

The characteristics of the companies mentioned in Ahmed, Yusof & Oroumchian's study, match the results acquired from the interview in this research. In fact, logistics is one of the industries that can get the most out of BI due to the large data sets that are available. Trieu's framework for measuring BI is therefore a valid way of measuring the added value of BI within the logistics industry.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, A., Yusof, S. A. M., & Oroumchian, F. (2019). Understanding the Business Value Creation Process for Business Intelligence Tools in the UAE. *Pacific Asia Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 11(3).
- Anderegg, W. R., Callaway, E. S., Boykoff, M. T., Yohe, G., & Root, T. Y. L. (2014). Awareness of both type 1 and 2 errors in climate science and assessment. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 95(9), 1445-1451.
- Barreto, L., Amaral, A., & Pereira, T. (2017). Industry 4.0 implications in logistics: an overview. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 13, 1245-1252.
- Trieu, V. H. (2017). Getting value from Business Intelligence systems: A review and research agenda. *Decision Support Systems*, 93, 111-124.
- Kallio, H., Pietilä, A., Johnson, M., & Kangasniemi, M. (2016). Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 72(12), 2954–2965.
- Leurent H., Enno B,(2018) *Beacons of Technology and Innovation in Industry 4.0*
- Yin, R., K. (2009) *Case Study Research. Design and Methods*. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, 4th edition 2009, pp. 240
- McCombes, S. (2019) *How to write a research methodology*. Scribbr
- Sekaran, U., Bougie, R. (2016) *Research Methods for Business*. John Wiley & Sons. pp.. 318

APPENDIX

Figure 1

